

Superficial Punctate Keratitis in Evaporative Dry Eye Syndrome

José Carlos Díaz Ramos^{1*}, Marta Villalba González¹, Antonio Cano Ortiz¹ and David Cerdán Palacios²

¹Hospital Arruzafa, Anterior Segment and Cornea Unity, Córdoba, Spain

²Hospital Arruzafa, R&D Unity, Córdoba, Spain

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Author : Dr. José Carlos Díaz Ramos, M.D.

Clinical Image

Corneal inflammation from various causes characterized by small scattered spots of loss or injury to the corneal epithelium, observed after instillation of sodium fluorescein dye and under cobalt blue filter illumination [1].

In this case, a 76-year-old woman with evaporative dry eye due to Meibomian gland dysfunction [2] and superficial punctate keratitis, Grade 2 according to Oxford scale, and a score of 20 on the OSDI test [3]. Her symptoms include redness, tearing, photophobia, slightly reduced vision, and eye fatigue. The patient was previously treated [4, 5] with Intense Pulsed Light (IPL) and is currently using local heat, cleansing wipes, and artificial tears as needed (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Dry Eye Syndrome.

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*Correspondence:

Dr. José Carlos Díaz Ramos, MD.,
Hospital Arruzafa, Anterior Segment
and Cornea Unity, Córdoba, Spain, Tel:
0034 957340118;

E-mail: drjcdiaz50k@gmail.com

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Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The Authors declare(s) that there is no conflict of interest.

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